

THE FOLLOWING CAN BE INCLUDED IN THE MAIN TASKS OF CORPORATE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: Taking into account the complex and contradictory nature of corporate governance, the problem of forming a mechanism for resolving conflicts and agreements between various participants of the corporate community and various bodies that manage its activities is of particular importance for the shareholders of the joint-stock company in our country.

Key words: Corporate management, conflict resolution mechanism, joint stock company, management.

In this regard, it is necessary to develop various types of codes that regulate the mechanism of corporate behavior, in particular, the issues of ensuring the interests of shareholders, the issues of the manager's accountability to the general meeting of the joint-stock company. According to the functions of the supervisory board in the organization of corporate management of joint-stock companies:

- It is recommended that every society have a document that defines the purpose, function, authority and responsibility of the council and includes the following basic rules:
- the core idea of the council is the formation of a group of individuals who conduct control work on behalf of property owners (shareholders) and other interested parties, free from business and other interactions with society and its activities.
- the mission of the board is the maximum growth of the value of the share invested by the shareholders. The goals and interests of the shareholders should be the basis of the board's activities.
- The task of the Council includes directing the activities of the Company on behalf of the shareholders and controlling the activities of its top managers (Management, General Director).

Broad attraction of foreign direct investments, radical improvement of the efficiency of joint-stock companies, ensuring their openness and attractiveness for future investors, introduction of modern corporate management methods, strengthening the role of shareholders in the strategic management of enterprises creates favorable conditions for

Based on these, the following are defined as the main directions of further development of the corporate management system:

- in-depth analysis of international experience and introduction of modern corporate management methods on this basis, increasing the efficiency of use of production, investment, material, technical, financial and labor resources is convenient for the establishment of joint-stock companies with the participation of foreign capital, wide attraction of foreign investments in joint-stock companies creating conditions;
- radical reorganization of the management structure of joint-stock companies, taking into account the termination of old divisions and positions, the introduction of new divisions and positions in accordance with modern international standards and the requirements of the market economy, strategic management of joint-stock companies, effective control of management personnel increasing the role of shareholders, including minority shareholders, in ensuring;
- increasing the efficiency of joint-stock companies' activities and improving the corporate management system;
- recommendations on the introduction of advanced methods of corporate management, including long-term development strategies and tasks, internal control systems and the establishment of effective interaction mechanisms of the executive body with shareholders and investors; introduction of a model organizational structure, taking into account the scope, industry characteristics and directions of joint-stock companies;
- in-depth analysis of international experience and, on this basis, introduction of modern corporate management methods, improvement of efficiency of use of production, investment, material and technical, financial and labor resources;
- establishment of joint-stock companies with the participation of foreign capital, creation of favorable conditions for wide attraction of foreign investments in joint-stock companies;
- radical reorganization of the management structure of joint-stock companies, taking into account the liquidation of old divisions and positions, the introduction of new divisions and positions in accordance with modern international standards and the requirements of the market economy;
- increasing the role of shareholders in the strategic management of joint-stock companies, ensuring effective control of management staff;
- training management staff based on cooperation with leading foreign educational institutions and raising their professional level, as well as attracting highly qualified foreign managers to leadership positions in joint-stock companies.

One of the important directions of the reform process in Uzbekistan is the privatization of state-owned enterprises by turning them into joint-stock companies and the creation of a management mechanism specific to new economic relations. It is known that corporate management is one of the management methods organized on the basis of the laws, demands and offers of the market economy.

The development of the level of production on a corporate basis is a new, unexplored problem for the Republic of Uzbekistan. In its study, the organization of corporate governance in foreign countries, its aspects and mechanisms, organizational structures of corporations, management technology, strategic development and corporate shareholders' funds. We should make extensive use of the existing experience in the field of organization of management.

The effective result of corporate management is not ensured only by good organization of management. The effectiveness of corporate management depends in many ways on the current state of the national economy, the improvement of the level of institutional management based on the economic and social situation, the state's policy in this direction, and the capabilities of managers to organize management.

Taking into account the complex and conflicting nature of corporate governance, the problem of forming a mechanism for resolving conflicts and agreements between various participants of the corporate community and various bodies that manage its activities is of particular importance for the shareholders of the joint-stock company in our country. In this regard, it is necessary to develop various types of codes that regulate the mechanism of corporate behavior, in particular, the issues of ensuring the interests of shareholders, the issues of the manager's accountability to the general meeting of the joint-stock company. The application of such codes to the activities of the joint-stock company has been widely implemented abroad, and methodological manuals and recommendations have been developed by state bodies and non-governmental organizations on corporate codes of conduct, corporate ethics and business relations issues.

Conclusion: Ensuring the stable development of the economy depends only on the formation of corporate relations based on highly cultured management that can meet the needs of the time. Also, the formation of cultured corporate relations based on the national mentality is also related to the fundamental change of the former totalitarian, centralized bureaucratic management system and the implementation of social protection, taking into account the labor resources participating in production activities, the levels of work, and the levels of their specialization. . The development

of corporate ownership and corporate governance also affects the prices of corporate shares.

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